

Bank Bukopin Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

Shalshabilla Putri, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia

wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word "Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional" within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional based on journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 4 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer loyalty behavior; and (4) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

Banking is a financial institution that plays an important role in a country's economy. Banking can encourage economic growth through its main activities, namely collecting and distributing customer funds. In the current era, there are various financial institutions, both conventional and sharia. This condition of course creates very tight competition among financial institutions. One of the financial institutions in the banking world is Bank Bukopin.

Cooperative Commercial Bank, better known as Bank Bukopin, is a financial institution that was founded on July 10, 1970. Then, Bank Bukopin officially started operating on March 16, 1971. During its development, this cooperative merged with another cooperative so that its name changed to Bank Bukopin on January 2 1990. After that, the status of the institution which was originally a cooperative changed to a limited liability company. This company has several subsidiaries, one of which is Bank Syariah Bukopin (BSB). Bank Syariah Bukopin's operational activities include making products such as MSME financing, construction, trade, and others.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional use library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and

contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

PT Bank Bukopin is one of the oldest banks operating in Indonesia. Since 1970, this bank has gone through various eras. To be able to serve the needs of the community, PT Bank Bukopin developed its business unit by having a subsidiary, namely PT Bank Bukopin Syariah. In its operations, PT Bank Bukopin's main activities are collecting and distributing funds by saving and saving, as well as channeling public funds through financing and credit to the community. Apart from that, this bank also carries out general banking operational activities in the service sector.

Islamic Financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit *riba* (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial inclusion also supports the development of the Islamic Financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be

used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The research object is Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional based on the journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

In this chapter, we will review research mapping related to Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional using VOSviewer bibliometric studies and Library Research studies. Garuda website search results show that there are 128 accredited national publication article titles originating from Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional.

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional

From 2005 to 2022, there has been an increase in publications in 2021, namely 21 articles. However, in 2022, the number of publications will decrease to only 12 articles. In addition, there were periods from 2006 to 2008 and 2012

where no articles were published about Bank Bukopin. This shows that research regarding Bank Bukopin is still minimal and is not available every year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional by year

Year of Publication n	Publication n Articles	Year of Publication n	Publication n Articles	Year of Publication n	Publication n Articles
2005	1	2014	1	2019	16
2009	1	2015	10	2020	13
2010	1	2016	17	2021	22
2011	1	2017	17	2022	12
2013	5	2018	12		
Total 129					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 2 shows that there are 97 affiliates/institutions that publish articles related to Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional. Journal of Management and Business (JMB) is the journal that publishes the most research on Bank Bukopin, namely 9 articles.

Table 2. Institutes and Journals Publishing Scientific Publications Regarding PT Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
JMB: Journal of Management and Business	9
Accounting E-Journal	6
FEB Student Scientific Journal	3
Accounting E-Journal, Journal of Scientific Accounting Studies, Faculty of Economics, UNTAN (KIAFE), Industrial Engineering Online Journal, INFORMATION MANAGEMENT FOR EDUCATORS AND PROFESSIONALS: Journal of Information Management, Ecodemica Journal: Journal of Economics, Management and Business, Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics, EMBA Journal: Journal of Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research, EMT KITA Journal, Journal of Accounting Science and Research (JIRA), MIZAN Journal of Legal Studies, Journal of Management and Finance, Journal of Competent Management, Student Online Journal (JOM) in the Field of Social Sciences and Political Science, Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals, Maro: Journal of Sharia Economics and Business, and SENTIA 2016.	2
ACCOUNTABILITY, Al-Kharaj: Journal of Sharia Economics, Finance & Business, Al-Mal: Journal of Islamic Accounting and Finance, AT-TAWASSUTH: Journal of Islamic Economics, Banque Syar'i: Scientific Journal of Sharia Banking, BISMA: Journal of Business and Management, CAKRAWALA: HUMANITIES JOURNAL BINA SARANA INFORMATIKA, CIVITAS: Journal of Management Studies, Computer Based	1

Information Systems Journal, Dynamics of Financial and Banking Accounting, Economic Dynamics - Journal of Economics and Business, Diponegoro Law Journal, DIRHAM Journal of Islamic Economics, Ecobuss, Ekonis: Journal of Economics and Business, Economics, Finance, Investment and Sharia (EQUITY), SHARIA ECONOMICS: Journal of Economic Studies, El-Kahfi | Journal of Islamic Economics, Equator Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship (EJME), EQUILIBRIA, and FIPA: Accounting Education Scientific Forum, FLOW, GOING CONCERN: JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING RESEARCH, Growth, Indicators: Scientific Journal of Management and Business, Indonesian Journal of Economics Application (IJE), JEKPP (Journal of Economics, Finance and Public Policy), Jemasi: Journal of Management Economics and Accounting, JIAGABI (Journal of Commercial/Business Administration Sciences), JIES: Journal of Islamic Economics Studies, JIM UPB (Scientific Journal of Management at Putera Batam University), JISIP: Journal of Social Sciences and Education, JMB: Journal of Management and Business, JMM17: Journal of Economics and Management, Journal of Management and Business Review, Journal of Management Review, AGGREGATE JOURNAL, Journal of Business and Management Applications (JABM), JOURNAL OF BUSINESS AND DEVELOPMENT, Journal of Computech & Business (e-Journal), Journal of Da'wah Minutes, Journal of Economic & Business Dynamics, Journal of e-Communication, Journal of EKOBIS (Economic and Business studies), JURNAL EKOMBIS, Journal of Economics KIAT, Journal of Banking Management Economics, Journal of Economics and Islamic Business, EMPATI Journal, Gaussian Journal, Design & Construction Scientific Journal, Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics, Scientific Journal of Public Administration Science, Pamulang University Informatics Journal, Management & Agribusiness Journal, Management and Banking Journal (JUMPA), Entrepreneurship Management Journal, Journal Indonesian Retail Management (JMARI), Student Online Journal (JOM) in the Field of Economics, PROFIT JOURNAL, BUSINESS AND MANAGEMENT RESEARCH JOURNAL, Public Relations Research Journal, STIE Journal, Lex Jurnalica, Matua Journal, Science Tower, MONETARY - ACCOUNTING AND FINANCE JOURNAL, OECONOMICUS Journal of Economics, Optimal: Journal of Economics and Entrepreneurship, PALAR (Pakuan Law review), Paradigma, PREMISE LAW JURNAL, Private Law, Proceedings of FRIMA (Management and Accounting Scientific Research Festival), RELATION: ECONOMIC JOURNAL, Responsive: Journal of Thought and Research Administration, Social, Humanities and Public Policy, REVITALIZATION: Journal of Management Science, SI-MEN, Synergy: Business and Management Studies, SULTANIST: Journal of Management and Finance, Syi'ar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking, TANJUNGPURA LAW JOURNAL, Tasharruf:

Journal of Economics and Business of Islam, The Asian Journal of Technology Management (AJTM), The Indonesian Journal of Business Administration, UG Journal, ULIL ALBAB: Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal, Valuation: Scientific Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship, and Value: Journal of Management and Business.

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 shows that Susatyo Nugroho WP and Ruzikna are the most productive researchers, because each has written 2 articles about Bank Bukopin.

Table 3. Productivity of Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional researchers

Writer's name	Institution Name
Dwi Ndayani, Harianto Achsani, Noer Azam; Deddy P. Koesrindartoto, Mega Pratiwi; Muhammad Riza, Kudang Boro Seminar, Agus Maulana;	Bogor Agricultural Institute
Agustina, Ruslinda Afriana, Rizki Amalia	Banjarmasin National STIE
Ahyakudin	Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa University
Rizka Nur Aini, Muhammad Iqbal Surya Pratikto,	UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya
Alfindo Akerta, Hasan Bisri	UIN Sunan Djati Bandung
Amalia, Imam Fahrur Rozi, Rudy Ariyanto;	Malang State Polytechnic
Reza Anggraeni, Sigit Prihanto Utomo, Taudlikhul Afkar	PGRI Adibuana University Surabaya
Azni, Landes Yuanda, Zulhelmy M Hatta, Tatik Mariyanti; Azni, Landes Yuanda, Zulhelmy M Hatta, Tatik Mariyanti;	UIN Suska Riau
Meliawati, Bramantyo Djohanputro	Journal of Management and Business Review
Haris Al Amin, Hilmi, Elsa Rozana	Lhokseumawe State Polytechnic
Riri Hanifa, Anton Trianto, Mahdi Hendrich; Indah Mawarni;	Sjakhyakirti University, Palembang
Robbi, Meita Pragiwani	STIE Indonesia
Toni Butarbutar	Esa Unggul University
Isrial, Muhammad Iqbal	Mercu Buana University
Isrial, Muhammad Iqbal, Mochamad Heru Riza Chakim	Indonesian Retail Management Journal
Syarifah Fadila, Susi Hendriani, Yusni Maulida; Nico Partawijaya, Ruzikna; Dini Yolanda Putri, Susi Hendriani, Nuryanti; Redho Refdi Ferdian, Ruzikna	Riau University
Dina Refina, Dahlan, Sri Walny Rahayu	Syiah Kuala University
Kurniawati Mulyanti	UNISMA Bekasi
Indah Tri Wulandari, Devy Tartila;	IAIN Bukit Tinggi

Aprillia Kartini Sabijono, Herman Karamoy, Heince Wokas	Sam Ratulangi University
Eliana	STIE Sabang Aceh
Rieska Ernawati, Susatyo Nugroho WP; Mutiara Erliza Erwin, Susatyo Nugroho WP; Rahmani Azizah, Ika Zenita Ratnaningsih;	Diponegoro University
Rezha Donald Makawimbang; Kiki Fajrina Luthfyanti; Cunanda Ayu Oktiviane, Ananda Sabil Hussein;	Brawijaya University
Bogy Febriatmoko, Sartika Wulandari, Widhian Hardiyanti;	Stikubank University Semarang
Firstianty Wahyuhening Fibriany	Journal of Business and Management
Firstianty Wahyuhening Fibriany ¹ , Nur Hani Oktavia	Ecodemica Journal
Ahmad Muflih Saifuddin, Amrie Firmansyah	Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics
Guntur Ujito, Syafarudin Alwi	Indonesian Islamic University
Dhain Atulaka Rissa Asih Asmoro	Kadiri Islamic University
Wuri Handayani	Sangga Buana University
M. Zaky Mubarak Lubis	Imam Bonjol Islamic University, Padang
Tumini, Dedi Kustiawan	Panca Marga University, Probolinggo
Elly Lestari, Yuni Setyawati, Elisabeth Yustina	Tribhuwana Tunggaladewi
Ismail Marjuki	STIE Dharma Putra Pekanbaru
Sofyan Marwansyah	BSI Jakarta Secretarial and Management Academy
Maryadi	STIE NOBEL, Makassar
Deddy P. Koesrindartoto, Mega Pratiwi	Bandung Institute of Technology
M Yasser Arafat, Rachmat Septi Mezul	Pamulang University
Andi Kusuma Negara	Muhammadiyah University of Tangerang
Rina Nopianti	Bina Bangsa University
Riyan Nugraha, Dede Abdul Rozak	Galuh Ciamis University
Eka Travilta Oktaria	Mitra Indonesia University
Made Dwi Pradipta Utama, Maria M. Ratna Sari;	Udayana University
Meyrina Ferdiana Putri, Sunan Fanani	Airlangga University
Gustami Lailatul Sukma, Tulus Rohana	Alumni of the Sukma College of Management Sciences
Ahmad Muflih Saifuddin, Amrie Firmansyah	STAN State Financial Polytechnic
Siti Aisah Sahlan, Didik Setiyadi	Journal of Information Management For Educators And Professionals

Lisda Silaban,	SULTANIST Journal
Sri Devi Apriani, Louisiana Mansoni	JEMPER (Economic Journal of Banking Management)
Sumarmi, Imam Sopingi, Tri Sudarwanto;	Hasyim Asy'ari University
Gustami Lailatul Sukma, Tulus Rohana;	Civitas: Journal of Management Studies
Khotibul Umam.	Tanjungpura Law Journal
Umar Haris, Julius Nursyamsi;	gunadarma University
Intan Utna Sari	Putera Batam University
Siti Wasiah	UINSA Surabaya
Rahmi Farah Diba Zulhas	Sriwijaya University

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Sharia and Conventional Bank Bukopin

Based on research articles from search results on the Garuda website (Garba Rujuka Digital) exported into RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using software VOSViewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps surrounding Bank Bukopin

Source: Processed data, VOSviewer 1.6.18 software.

co-word map network visualization of research developments regarding Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional are divided into 9 clusters and 16 4 topics, as follows:

- Cluster 1. Red covers 43 topics, namely: addition, assessment, career opportunity, bukopin, company, competition, corporate culture, customer, development, effectiveness, effort, employee, employee performance, human resource, influence, information, interest, internet banking, employees, leadership, leadership style, motivation, mpe, ocb, organizational communication, influence, performance, performance appraisal, PT Bank Bukopin Banda Aceh, quality, questionnaire, rapid application development, respondent, sample, satisfaction, sem, significance level, significant effect, spss version, system, technique, training, work motivation.
- Cluster 2. Green covers 32 topics, namely: asset quality, Bank Bukopin, capital, condition, data analysis technique, earnings, financial performance, financial ratio, financial statement, good corporate governance, growth, health, ldr, level, liquidity, loan, management, model, net interest margin, npl, profitability ratio, PT Bank Bukopin, PT Bank Bukopin Tbk, ratio, risk, roa, secondary data, tax, term, value, volatility.
- Cluster 3. Blue covers 17 topics, namely: analysis, assurance, customer loyalty, customer satisfaction, determination, empathy, independent variable, multiple linear regression, observation, population, reliability, responsiveness, service quality, spss study, t test, working capital turnover.
- Cluster 4. Yellow covers 16 topics, namely: agreement, applicant, bank, bank guarantee, bank guarantee, Bank Indonesia, collateral, debtor, developer, disbursement, guarantee, collateral, customer, recipient, respondent, case study.
- Cluster 5. Purple covers 15 topics, namely: asset, bopo, CAR, cost, deposit ratio, fdr, financing, income, mudharabah, NPF, performing financing, return, third party fund, variable.
- Cluster 6. Light blue covers 11 topics, namely: according, Bank Bukopin Padang, corporate social responsibility, data, debt, implementation, employees, PT Bank Syariah Bukopin, research, research method.
- Cluster 7. Orange covers 11 topics, namely: acquisition, Bank Bukopin Tbk, coefficient, internal control, issue, method, monopolistic practice, relationship, researcher, tbk, unfair business competition.
- Cluster 8. Dark purple covers 10 topics, namely: Bukopin Bank, consumer, factor, functional quality, hypothesis testing, loans distribution, period, profitability, service, technical quality.
- Cluster 9. The pink color covers 9 topics, namely: amount, Bank Bukopin Medan Setia Budi, credit, effect, fund, micro business customer, path analysis, company, profit.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Bukopin's Financial Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 13 topics related to the financial performance of Bank Bukopin Syariah, namely:

First, the influence of financial reports on predictions of company bankruptcy. Bank Bukopin's financial reports include a balance sheet, profit and loss statement and cash flow. Financial statement analysis helps in measuring a bank's financial health and can help in predicting potential

company bankruptcy. Several financial ratios used to measure company bankruptcy are: (1) Current Ratio: Measures the company's ability to meet its short-term obligations. (2) Debt to Equity Ratio: Measures the extent to which a company finances its assets with debt. (3) Profit to Sales Ratio: Measures the company's ability to generate profits from sales. (4) Net Profit to Equity Ratio: Measures the efficiency of using company equity in generating profits.

Second, the system for determining financing feasibility. At Bank Bukopin, this process will involve credit analysis and risk assessment to determine whether potential borrowers can follow payment obligations in a timely manner. Several factors that may be considered in the process of determining the feasibility of financing at Bank Bukopin are: (1) Customer credit history: Including records of previous debt payments and previous credit quality. (2) Income and repayment capacity: Evaluate whether the prospective borrower has sufficient income to repay the loan. (3) Financing objective: To ensure that the use of funds is understood and in accordance with customer needs. (4) Security: If the requested financing requires collateral, the bank will assess the value and quality of the collateral submitted.

Third, the influence of the inflation rate, Third Party Funds/DPK, financing on income. (1) If the inflation rate is high, the value of the currency will decrease, which can have a negative impact on bank revenues due to reduced customer purchasing power, the potential for bad credit, and fluctuations in the value of bank assets. (2) If TPF increases, banks will have more funds to use in operations and provide financing, which can have a positive impact on income. (3) The amount and quality of financing provided by banks will also affect income. Good and healthy financing can increase bank income, while problematic financing can cause losses and reduce income.

Fourth, the influence of profitability and leverage on Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR. (1) If Bank Bukopin experiences good profitability, it means they have consistent and sustainable profits. This can provide an opportunity for banks to be more active in carrying out CSR programs by using part of their profits to make positive contributions to society and the environment. (2) If Bank Bukopin has high leverage (significant debt levels), its financial risk may increase. This could limit banks' ability to actively participate in CSR programs as they must focus on managing debt and reducing financial risks.

Fifth, the influence of Third Party Funds/TPF, Fee Based Income, Non Performing Financing/NPF, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Overhead costs on financing.

Sixth, the effect of profit sharing, Non Performing Financing/NPF, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Mudharabah financing, Musyarakah financing, Murabahah financing, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO, BI Rate, Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance/GCG, Net Operating Margin/NOM on profitability. (1) Profit Sharing is a method of sharing profits between sharia banks and their customers. When Bank Bukopin Syariah succeeds in managing Profit Sharing contracts efficiently, this can increase the bank's profitability because it can attract more customers who are interested in the profit sharing system. (2) NPF refers to the part of the financing that cannot be repaid by the customer on time. High NPF can cause a decrease in profitability because banks have to bear losses due to problematic financing. (3) FDR describes the ratio between total financing and total third party funds received by the bank. A high ratio can indicate that the bank is too dependent on third party funds and is at risk of lacking liquidity. This can affect profitability due to high funding costs. (4)

Mudharabah, Musyarakah and Murabahah financing are financing methods in sharia banks. Well-managed financing can increase bank profits, especially if credit risk is managed well. (5) CAR is a ratio that measures a bank's ability to bear credit risk. If Bank Bukopin Syariah's CAR is low, then the bank may have to hold more capital to cover risks, which could affect profitability by reducing the bank's ability to provide financing. (6) BOPO measures bank operational efficiency. The lower the BOPO, the more efficiently the bank manages its operational costs, which can contribute to increased profitability. (7) BI Rate is the reference interest rate set by Bank Indonesia. Changes in the BI Rate can affect funding costs and bank financing interest rates. If the BI Rate rises, bank funding costs will also rise, which can affect bank profitability. (8) The bank's risk profile describes the extent to which the bank understands and is able to manage the risks it faces. Good risk management can help reduce potential losses and negative impacts on profitability. (9) GCG refers to good corporate governance. Banks with good GCG practices tend to have transparent, accountable and responsible management, which can increase customer and investor confidence and increase profitability. (10) NOM is the difference between operational income and bank operational costs. A high NOM shows that the bank is able to generate more profits from its operations, which can increase profitability.

Seventh, the influence of Mudharabah profit sharing income and Murabahah margin income on company profits. (1) The effect of Mudharabah profit sharing income on Bank Bukopin's company profits will depend greatly on the performance of the investments made by the bank. If the investment is successful in providing profits, the bank will get higher income from Mudharabah and can increase company profits. (2) The influence of Murabahah margin income on company profits is as a source of bank profit sharing income. Bank Bukopin will benefit from the difference in selling and buying prices of goods financed through the Murabahah mechanism.

Eighth, the influence of Murabahah financing and Istishna' financing on fund distribution income. (1) The effect of Murabahah financing on fund distribution income is that the bank will obtain income from the financing transaction and allocate the funds to meet the financing needs of other customers. (2) The effect of Istishna' financing on fund distribution income is that the bank will obtain income from the difference in selling price and production costs of goods. This income will become part of the funds that can be redistributed to finance other customer needs.

Ninth, the level of soundness of financial performance using the RGEC method. The following is the explanation: (1) Risk Profile: Refers to the risk assessment faced by the bank. This includes credit risk, market risk, operational risk and other relevant risks. Banks that have a good risk profile tend to be more stable and have controlled risk potential. (2) Good Corporate Governance: Assessing the quality of bank governance and management. Good corporate governance includes transparency, accountability, effective supervision, and compliance with regulations and policies. (3) Earnings (Profit Performance): Measures the bank's ability to generate profits from its operations. Good profit performance indicates a healthy and competitive bank. (4) Capital: Refers to the amount of capital owned by the bank to cover the risks it faces. Sufficient capital is important to maintain the stability and continuity of the bank's business.

Tenth, the influence of inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, Gross Domestic Product/GDP, profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits. (1) Inflation is

an increase in the general price of goods and services in an economy within a certain period of time. Inflation can affect Mudharabah deposits at Bank Bukopin by reducing the purchasing power of the value of customer funds. An increase in inflation will cause the value of customers' money to tend to decrease over time, so that Mudharabah deposits with a fixed profit rate may experience a decrease in purchasing power. (2) The interest rate is the cost of borrowing or profits from holding funds measured in percentages. Interest rates can affect Mudharabah deposits at Bank Bukopin. If interest rates rise, the profit sharing received by Mudharabah deposit customers also tends to rise, and conversely, if interest rates fall, profit sharing tends to decrease. (3) The exchange rate is a comparison of the value of one country's currency with another country's currency. Exchange rate fluctuations can have an impact on Mudharabah deposits at Bank Bukopin, especially if customer funds or profits earned are converted into other currencies. Changes in exchange rates may cause changes in the value of customer investments in local currency. (4) GDP is a measure of the total value of goods and services produced by a country in a certain period. GDP can influence Mudharabah deposits at Bank Bukopin through indications of economic growth. Good economic growth tends to increase customer confidence, which can have a positive impact on the number and size of deposits invested. (5) Profit sharing is the profit given by Bank Bukopin to Mudharabah deposit customers as part of the profits generated from the investment. The level of profit sharing can be influenced by investment performance and overall economic performance.

Eleventh, the influence of the Quality of Productive Assets/KAP, Third Party Funds/DPK, Liabilities on Earnings After Tax. (1) Productive Asset Quality refers to the quality of Bank Bukopin's loan and investment portfolio. If KAP decreases, it means that the number of problematic or bad loans increases, which can have a negative impact on the bank's income and performance. This can affect the Bank's ability to provide greater profits on Mudharabah deposits. (2) DPK reflects the amount of funds collected by the Bank from customers through savings, deposits and other sources of funds. The higher the TPF, the greater the source of funds available to the Bank for use in operations and investments. With high DPK, Bank Bukopin can provide better benefits to Mudharabah deposit customers. (3) Liabilities are financial obligations owned by the Bank, including debts and other obligations. A high level of liabilities can increase the Bank's financial risk. In this case, banks may be more careful in offering high profit sharing on Mudharabah deposits so that financial risks can be minimized.

Twelfth, level of efficiency with Aggressive Data Envelopment Analysis. In the context of Bank Bukopin, Aggressive DEA is used to evaluate the extent to which the bank can optimize the use of resources (such as capital, labor and assets) to achieve desired results/outputs, such as income or profit levels. The results of the DEA Aggressive analysis will help banks to identify potential efficiency that can be improved, as well as take the necessary actions to improve operational performance.

Thirteenth, the influence of Mudharabah and Murabahah financing on net profits. The effect of Mudharabah and Murabahah financing on net profits at Bank Bukopin will depend greatly on a number of factors, including the level of customer participation in these two types of financing, the size of profits generated from Mudharabah transactions and the price difference received from Murabahah transactions. If Bank Bukopin succeeds in attracting many customers to participate in Mudharabah financing and is able to create

Murabahah transactions with profitable price differences, then these two types of financing can contribute positively to the bank's net profits. However, if there are risk factors or operational obstacles in implementing this financing, the impact on net profits may be reduced. Therefore, Bank Bukopin management needs to conduct an in-depth analysis of the performance of these two types of financing to understand their impact on overall net profits.

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 10 topics related to the financial performance of Bank Bukopin Conventional, namely:

First, forecasting volatility in stock returns using Asymmetric Power Autoregression Conditional Heteroskedasticity/APARCH. Bank Bukopin uses the APARCH model to forecast volatility in stock returns. APARCH is a type of model in time series analysis that is used to model the volatility of financial assets such as shares. The uniqueness of the APARCH model is its ability to overcome asymmetries in volatility, meaning that increases or decreases in stock prices can have different impacts on their volatility. The APARCH model utilizes an autoregressive approach to predict future volatility based on past volatility. In addition, this model also considers the conditional component of heteroskedasticity, which refers to changes in variability in data over time. Thus, Bank Bukopin can use APARCH to identify volatility patterns in stock returns, which can assist in investment decision making and risk management.

Second, the company's financial performance uses financial ratios. Bank Bukopin uses financial ratios as a tool to analyze and measure the company's financial performance. Financial ratios are numbers or comparisons calculated from relevant financial data and can provide insight into the financial health of a company. Financial ratios can provide an overview of operational efficiency, profitability, liquidity, solvency and the effectiveness of a company's risk management.

Third, the influence of Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Non-Performing Loans/NPL, Return on Assets/ROA, Operational Costs on Operational Income/BOPO on capital adequacy. (1) A high LDR can cause liquidity risk, because if there are large withdrawals from customers, the bank may have difficulty meeting its credit obligations. In this case, a balanced LDR must be implemented to ensure adequate liquidity for bank capital adequacy. (2) High NPLs can indicate poor asset quality and increase credit risk for the bank. High NPLs can also affect bank capital adequacy because banks have to allocate more capital to cover the risk of uncollectible credit. (3) Low ROA can indicate a lack of efficiency in generating income from bank assets, which in turn can affect the bank's capital adequacy. (4) A high BOPO indicates large operational costs compared to operating income, which can reduce the bank's net profit and impact capital adequacy.

Fourth, calculation and accounting for interest on deposits and savings. In its operational activities, Bank Bukopin carries out accounting calculations and records related to deposit and savings interest. This process involves several stages: (1) Calculation of interest: The bank will calculate the interest that must be paid to its customers based on the interest percentage agreed upon in the contract. Deposit interest is usually calculated based on a fixed interest rate, while savings interest may vary according to the balance and applicable interest rates. (2) Transaction recording: After the interest calculation is complete, Bank Bukopin will record the transaction in their accounting system. This information includes the amount of interest that must be paid to customers and changes in their savings or deposit balances. (3) Reporting to customers: Bank

Bukopin will also provide periodic reports to customers showing details of the interest received and their account balances. (4) Reporting to authorities: Banks must also ensure that their interest calculations and accounting records comply with applicable regulatory provisions and accounting standards.

Fifth, the influence of net profit and cash flow on cash dividends. If the bank's net profit is high, then the bank has the potential to distribute more cash dividends to shareholders. Positive cash flow can increase the bank's ability to pay cash dividends to shareholders.

Sixth, the influence of stock prices and credit control on company health using the CAMEL method. If Bank Bukopin's share price increases, this shows that investors and the market as a whole have a positive view of the bank's future performance and growth. An increase in share prices can indicate that the bank has succeeded in achieving good financial performance, operational efficiency and the right business strategy. Apart from that, high share prices can also strengthen the bank's capital position and provide benefits to shareholders. On the other hand, if Bank Bukopin's share price declines, this could indicate that there is concern from the market about the company's performance and prospects. Share price declines can result from a variety of factors, including weak financial performance, high credit risk, management problems, or economic uncertainty affecting the banking industry as a whole.

Seventh, the influence of working capital turnover and accounts receivable turnover on profitability. Good credit control is an important key in ensuring company health. If Bank Bukopin has an effective credit control system, credit risk can be managed well, and the possibility of problematic or bad credit can be minimized. Factors analyzed in credit control include credit granting policies, credit worthiness analysis, regular credit monitoring, credit portfolio diversification, and efficiency in collecting receivables from problematic customers. By implementing good credit control, Bank Bukopin can reduce credit risk and improve the quality of its assets.

Eighth, the influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Non-Performing Loans/NPL on profitability. (1) The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's level of security in facing possible losses. A fairly high CAR shows that the bank has the financial strength to bear risk and can operate more stably. An increase in CAR will usually have a positive impact on profitability, because the credit risks faced by banks can be better managed. (2) If the LDR is high, it means that the bank is providing more loans than the funds collected, and this can increase liquidity risk. A high LDR can have a negative impact on profitability because banks may need to pay higher interest rates to attract funds from outside if the supply of funds from deposits is insufficient. (3) A high NPL indicates that the bank faces high credit risk and can affect profitability because the bank has to face losses due to default. If NPLs can be managed well, credit risk can be reduced and have a positive impact on profitability.

Ninth, the influence of cost of funds, interest income and liquidity ratio on profitability. (1) The higher the cost of funds, the greater the interest burden that the bank must bear, which can reduce profitability. Banks need to look for ways to optimize the cost of funds in order to obtain funds at lower interest rates and increase profitability. (2) Interest income is one of the main sources of income for banks. An increase in interest income can increase a bank's profitability, especially if it can be balanced with an efficient cost of funds. (3) A good liquidity ratio indicates that the bank has sufficient liquidity to meet customer withdrawals when needed. A low liquidity ratio can cause a bank to

have difficulty meeting obligations, and it may need to pay higher interest to attract short-term funds. This can affect bank profitability.

Tenth, petty cash disbursement information system. Some of the features that may be contained in this system include: (1) Detailed transaction recording: This system will record each petty cash disbursement transaction in detail, including transaction description, date, amount and recipient. (2) Authorization and approval: This system usually involves an authorization and approval process by authorized parties before small transactions can be carried out, to ensure that the expenditure is legal and in accordance with bank policy. (3) Reporting: This system can also provide reporting features to facilitate monitoring and analysis of overall petty cash expenditures. (4) Integration with financial systems: Data from the petty cash disbursement information system can be integrated with the bank's overall financial system, thereby facilitating the accounting and financial reporting process.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Bukopin Employee Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 2 topics related to the performance of Bank Bukopin Syariah employees, namely:

First, management audit. In the context of Bank Bukopin, management audits can focus on evaluating various aspects of management, such as resource use, process efficiency, and compliance with policies and regulations. If Bank Bukopin employees have good performance in facing management audits, it means they are able to carry out their duties well, have a deep understanding of existing work processes, and comply with the policies and rules set by the company. Employees who are able to pass a management audit with satisfactory results show that they can make a positive contribution in carrying out their functions and responsibilities.

Second, work incentives. Work incentives can be in the form of bonuses, allowances, or other facilities given as a reward for good performance. Bank Bukopin employees who receive appropriate work incentives will tend to be more motivated to achieve targets and perform high. Fair and transparent incentives will create a positive work environment and increase enthusiasm for work.

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 21 topics related to the performance of Bank Bukopin Conventional employees, namely:

First, professional commitment. Bank Bukopin employees who have high professional commitment will try to provide the best service to customers, maintain work ethics, and always strive to improve their competence. Employees with strong professional commitment will tend to provide consistent and high quality performance in carrying out their duties, which in turn will increase customers' reputation and trust in Bank Bukopin.

Second, organizational commitment. Bank Bukopin employees who have high organizational commitment will feel connected and contribute positively to achieving organizational goals. Employees who have strong organizational commitment will work with enthusiasm, collaborate with teams, and strive to advance Bank Bukopin as an institution.

Third, organizational communication. Good communication ensures that all employees understand the goals, strategies and latest developments of Bank Bukopin. Employees who work in an environment with effective organizational communication will more easily understand their role in achieving company

goals. This can improve coordination, efficiency and collaboration across the organization.

Fourth, transformational leadership. Bank Bukopin's transformational leader will mobilize employee enthusiasm to innovate, adapt to change, and achieve superior performance. Employees led by transformational leaders will feel more enthusiastic, confident, and motivated to make significant contributions in their work environment.

Fifth, work motivation. Bank Bukopin employees who have high work motivation will work diligently, focus on achieving results, and be persistent in overcoming challenges. Bank Bukopin management can encourage employee work motivation by providing recognition for achievements, career development opportunities, and creating an inclusive and supportive work environment.

Sixth, organizational citizenship behavior/OCB. In the context of Bank Bukopin, OCB can include employees who actively help colleagues in completing tasks, provide support to the team, and actively contribute to social activities inside and outside the company. Employees who demonstrate high OCB can create a positive work atmosphere and have an impact on productivity and overall employee satisfaction.

Seventh, organizational culture. A strong culture that encourages collaboration, innovation and integrity can have a positive impact on employee performance. If employees feel they fit into the organizational culture and can adapt well, they tend to be more motivated to give their best in their work.

Eighth, personality type. Employees who are extroverted and proactive may be more enthusiastic about interacting with customers, while employees who tend to be introverted may excel at data analysis and more structured work. It is important for Bank Bukopin to recognize employee personality types and place them in roles that suit their skills and preferences.

Ninth, work enthusiasm. Employees who have high work morale tend to be more dedicated, productive, and focused on achieving company goals. Bank Bukopin can encourage work morale by giving appreciation for employee achievements, providing development opportunities, and creating a supportive work environment.

Tenth, career development. When employees feel they have opportunities to develop their skills and abilities, they tend to be more motivated to improve their performance. Bank Bukopin can provide training and development programs, mentoring, and clear career paths to increase employee motivation and performance.

Eleventh, performance assessment. With an objective performance appraisal, employees will have a clear picture of their performance and can identify areas where they need to improve. Bank Bukopin can use performance appraisals as a tool to provide constructive feedback and design development plans for employees who need additional support.

Twelfth, interpersonal relationships. Employees at Bank Bukopin need to be able to communicate and work together well in teams, so as to create effective collaboration to achieve common goals.

Thirteenth, work environment. Bank Bukopin must ensure that employees have access to the facilities and resources necessary to carry out their duties efficiently. Apart from that, support from management and coworkers is also important in creating a positive work environment.

Fourteenth, compensation. Employees who feel appreciated with appropriate compensation for their contributions tend to be more motivated to

work hard and perform high. The right incentive system can also be used to encourage superior performance and extraordinary achievements.

Fifteenth, profit. Employees who succeed in achieving or even exceeding predetermined profit targets demonstrate effectiveness in carrying out their duties and responsibilities, whether in selling banking products, customer service, or managing risk well.

Sixteenth, training. Bank Bukopin employees who receive regular training can develop their skills and knowledge in various fields, such as banking products and services, the latest technology, and leadership skills. Employees who are knowledgeable and constantly updated will be more efficient and productive in their work.

Seventeenth, job crafting. If employees are given the opportunity to do job crafting, they can feel more enthusiastic and motivated to achieve better results. In the context of Bank Bukopin, employees who can restructure their duties to suit their talents and skills may be able to make a more significant contribution to the bank.

Eighteenth, psychological empowerment. Employees who feel psychologically empowered will tend to innovate more, dare to take necessary risks, and be more motivated to achieve desired results. In a stressful environment like the banking industry, psychological empowerment is critical to maintaining employee mental well-being.

Nineteenth, work ability. This includes technical skills, communication, collaboration, and adaptability. Bank Bukopin employees who have good work abilities will be able to carry out their duties efficiently and effectively, thereby contributing to the bank's overall productivity and performance.

Twentieth, career opportunities. Bank Bukopin, which provides a clear career path and provides promotion opportunities for employees who excel, will encourage employees to work harder and achieve personal and organizational goals.

Twenty-one, taxpayer compliance. Good taxpayer compliance shows that employees understand the importance of complying with applicable laws and regulations, thereby minimizing the risk of violations and avoiding potential legal problems that could harm the bank's reputation and operations.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Bukopin Customer Loyalty Behavior

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 3 topics related to the loyalty behavior of Bank Bukopin Syariah customers, namely:

First, product quality. Customer behavior at Bank Bukopin is influenced by the quality of the products offered. Product quality includes various aspects such as interest, interest rates, administration fees, product features, and so on. If Bank Bukopin offers quality products, customers tend to be more interested in using their services and products sustainably.

Second, sales promotion. Effective sales promotions from Bank Bukopin can influence customer behavior in terms of awareness about the products and services offered. If promotions are carried out well, such as discount programs, prizes or other attractive offers, customers will feel more interested in using Bank Bukopin services and increase their banking activities.

Third, service quality. Good service quality is one of the important factors influencing customer behavior. If Bank Bukopin provides friendly, fast and

professional service, customers will feel more satisfied and tend to continue using their services, and can even recommend this bank to others.

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 14 topics related to the loyalty behavior of Bank Bukopin Conventional customers, namely:

First, technical quality. Technical quality relates to banking systems and infrastructure. If Bank Bukopin has a stable, safe and sophisticated system, customers will feel more confident in carrying out their banking transactions and tend to use this bank's services repeatedly.

Second, functional quality. Functional quality emphasizes the efficiency and effectiveness of services. Customers want banking services that are easy to use and help them achieve their financial goals. If Bank Bukopin's functional services meet customer expectations, this can increase customer loyalty and satisfaction levels.

Third, internet banking. In today's digital era, internet banking plays an important role in customer behavior. If Bank Bukopin provides a safe, comfortable and complete internet banking platform, customers will be more inclined to access their accounts online and carry out various transactions through the platform.

Fourth, establishing a credit card target market. The strategy for establishing a credit card target market will influence the behavior of customers who are interested in this service. If Bank Bukopin targets the right market segment and offers attractive benefits and incentives for using credit cards, potential customers will be interested in applying for a credit card from this bank.

Fifth, convenience. The ease of using banking services can be an attraction for customers. If Bank Bukopin provides convenience in the process of opening accounts, transactions and accessing other services, customers will feel more helped and may continue to use this bank's services.

Sixth, usefulness. Customer behavior regarding usefulness is related to how customers assess the benefits or benefits they get from using Bank Bukopin products or services. Customers will tend to be more interested in making transactions or saving money at the bank if they feel that the products and services provided provide added value and benefit their financial needs.

Seventh, risk. Customer behavior is also influenced by how they perceive the risks associated with using Bank Bukopin products and services. Customers will be more inclined to interact with banks and make transactions if they feel the risks are under control and in line with their risk tolerance. Banks need to provide clear information regarding the risks of their products and services to build customer trust.

Eighth, trust. Trust is an important factor in shaping customer behavior. Customers will be more inclined to commit to Bank Bukopin if they feel the bank is reliable and has a good reputation in providing financial services. Trust can be built through integrity, transparency and consistent service quality.

Ninth, marketing communications. Effective marketing communications from Bank Bukopin can influence customer behavior. If banks are able to convey information about their products and services well, and provide relevant and attractive offers, customers will be more motivated to choose products or services from that bank.

Tenth, legal protection of personal data. Legal protection of personal data is an important factor for customer behavior in this digital era. Customers will feel more safe and comfortable interacting with Bank Bukopin if the bank

properly maintains the confidentiality of their personal data and complies with applicable regulations regarding data privacy.

Eleventh, customer relationship management. With good CRM, Bank Bukopin can increase customer loyalty by providing a personalized service experience and better meeting customer needs. Customer behavior can be influenced by the quality of interactions and relationships built through CRM.

Twelfth, customer value. Bank Bukopin will focus more on customers who provide more value to the bank, for example through more active transactions, storing larger funds, or using paid services. This can influence customer behavior because they feel better treated and appreciated by the bank if they provide high marks.

Thirteenth, People's Business Credit/KUR. Customer behavior regarding People's Business Credit (KUR) can vary. For customers who have small or micro businesses, KUR can be an opportunity to gain access to capital more easily and with lower interest. Customer behavior regarding KUR can be influenced by an easy application process, clear requirements and competitive interest rates.

Fourteenth, credit card services. Customer behavior regarding credit card services will be influenced by the quality of the services provided. Customers will tend to be more active in using credit cards if they feel they are well served, get attractive offers, and have the convenience of managing their credit cards.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues at Bank Bukopin

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 8 research topics related to issues at Bank Bukopin Syariah, namely:

First, the application of PSAK 105 in Mudharabah financing. In implementing PSAK 105, Bank Bukopin must follow sharia rules and principles to record mudharabah transactions and agreements and ensure proper disclosure in financial reports.

Second, the company's responsibility towards stakeholders from an Islamic perspective. From an Islamic perspective, Bank Bukopin as a company has social responsibility towards all its stakeholders. Stakeholders include shareholders, customers, employees, government, society and the environment. Companies must prioritize the principles of justice, transparency and Islamic ethics in their business relationships. For example, providing services and products that comply with sharia, providing reasonable benefits for customers, paying fair wages to employees, and paying attention to the social and environmental impacts of company operations.

Third, resolving problem loans in People's Business Credit/KUR. When problematic credit occurs in the KUR program, Bank Bukopin needs to follow the procedures and conditions that have been established, including re-assessing customers who are having difficulty paying credit. Banks can also carry out credit restructuring or negotiations to find joint solutions. The main aim is to avoid the accumulation of bad credit and help MSMEs overcome their financial problems.

Fourth, the application of sharia principles to sharia bank operations from a financing perspective. As a sharia bank, Bank Bukopin must follow sharia principles in all aspects of its operations, including financing. Some sharia principles that must be adhered to are: (1) Prohibition of usury: Interest or compound interest is not permitted in financing. (2) Prohibition of maysir and gharar: Transactions involving excessive speculation and uncertainty are not permitted. (3) Profit sharing: In financing such as mudharabah or musharakah,

profits and risks are shared fairly according to the agreement. Banks also need to ensure that the financing provided is in accordance with sharia principles and is oriented towards justice and the common good.

Fifth, Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR reporting from the perspective of Sharia Enterprise Theory. In the context of CSR, Bank Bukopin must report on social and environmental activities carried out by following sharia principles, such as helping people in need, investing in environmentally friendly projects, and contributing to sustainable socio-economic development. CSR reports must include initiatives and programs that are in accordance with Islamic values and have a positive impact on society.

Sixth, the application of the Murabahah agreement to pension financing. In the context of pension financing, customers can choose a murabahah contract to invest their pension funds in assets that are halal and comply with sharia principles. The profits from this investment can be expected to help finance the customer's retirement life.

Seventh, the law on refusing to disburse bank guarantees. Refusal to disburse the bank guarantee may occur if the conditions in the bank guarantee are not fulfilled or there is a discrepancy with the applicable provisions. However, to ensure the legality of refusing to disburse bank guarantees from a sharia perspective, Bank Bukopin must ensure that the reasons for the refusal are in accordance with applicable sharia provisions and principles. The bank must ensure that the refusal of disbursement is carried out fairly and based on objective considerations and in accordance with the signed agreement.

Eighth, application of istishna' accounting. In implementing istishna' accounting, the Bank must follow sharia principles in recording these transactions. Benefits and risks must be determined clearly and fairly in the agreement between the Bank and customers who need istishna' financing. In addition, transparent disclosure is also required in financial reports to ensure compliance with sharia principles.

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 15 research topics related to issues at Bank Bukopin Conventional, namely:

First, a credit scoring model for the process of analyzing the feasibility of home ownership credit facilities. Bank Bukopin uses a credit scoring model to analyze the feasibility of providing home ownership credit facilities to prospective customers. The credit scoring model is an assessment system that is based on data and information held by prospective customers, such as personal data, financial data and previous credit history (if any). This model will provide a credit score to prospective customers based on the level of risk or ability to repay the credit. This credit score is a consideration for banks to determine whether a credit application will be approved or rejected, as well as determining interest rates and other credit terms.

Second, accounting information systems in management analysis of credit distribution. Bank Bukopin uses a sophisticated accounting information system to support the management analysis process in lending. This system allows banks to collect, manage and analyze data related to credit distribution efficiently and accurately. With complete and timely information, management can evaluate credit performance, identify credit trends, and make strategic decisions regarding better credit distribution. This also helps banks control credit risk and optimize their credit portfolio.

Third, the influence of credit prerequisites on smooth payments. Credit prerequisites are the terms and conditions that must be fulfilled by the borrower

before obtaining a credit facility. The influence of credit prerequisites on the smoothness of payments is closely related to the borrower's ability to fulfill payment obligations on time according to the agreement. If credit prerequisites have been carefully considered and are in line with the borrower's financial profile and capacity, the likelihood of smooth repayment will increase. Bank Bukopin has strict procedures for assessing and determining credit prerequisites to minimize the risk of bad credit. Some credit prerequisites that are usually applied include minimum income requirements, collateral or collateral requirements, and a good credit report. By having appropriate prerequisites, banks can ensure that borrowers have the ability to repay credit smoothly.

Fourth, an internal control system for fraud and credit performance. Bank Bukopin has a strong internal control system to overcome potential fraud and fraud in the credit process. This system includes a series of procedures, policies and controls designed to detect, prevent and respond to fraudulent acts that may be committed by internal or external parties. Internal control also functions to monitor overall credit performance. This involves monitoring the credit portfolio, credit quality, level of non-performing loans, and regular credit risk measurements. With an effective internal control system, Bank Bukopin can reduce the risk of fraud and improve overall credit performance.

Fifth, determine credit risk using a decision tree. Decision trees are one of the methods of credit risk analysis used by Bank Bukopin. This method is a machine learning algorithm that describes the decision flow in the form of a tree structure. Each node in the tree represents a decision based on features or variables that are relevant in determining credit risk. Decision trees allow banks to understand the relationship between variables that influence credit risk and classify potential customers into certain risk categories. In this way, banks can more easily assess the credit risk of various potential customers and make more appropriate decisions in lending.

Sixth, Home Ownership Credit/KPR is related to guaranteeing a buy back guarantee by the developer. Home Ownership Credit (KPR) is a credit facility provided by Bank Bukopin to customers to buy a house or other property. In some cases, property developers who build houses or certain housing projects offer buy back guarantees to banks. Buy back guarantee is a guarantee from the developer to the bank that if the house or property purchased by the customer using a KPR experiences difficulties in being resold, the developer will buy the house back at a predetermined price. This provides additional protection for banks against liquidity risk and increases bank confidence in providing mortgage facilities to customers.

Seventh, solving problem loans through collateral offsets. Problematic credit is credit that experiences problems in paying installments on time or experiences significant delays in payment. To resolve problem loans, Bank Bukopin can use the collateral offset method. Collateral offset is the bank's action to use funds or collateral value that have been provided by customers as collateral to pay the remaining outstanding credit obligations. In this case, the bank will sell or liquidate the customer's collateral to cover problematic credit payments. In this way, banks can reduce the risk of non-performing loans and restore the health of their credit portfolios.

Eighth, the settlement requires credit guarantees. At Bank Bukopin, the process of completing obtaining credit guarantees refers to the actions or procedures that customers must go through to obtain approval or guarantees from the bank to obtain credit facilities. This means that before customers can

obtain credit from Bank Bukopin, they must meet certain requirements set by the bank, such as financial requirements, appropriate guarantees or collateral, and fulfill other relevant conditions.

Ninth, dispute resolution in accordance with article 55 UUPS. Article 55 UUPS refers to the Banking Law in Indonesia, and dispute resolution according to Article 55 UUPS refers to the mechanism or method of resolving disputes or conflicts between Bank Bukopin and its customers. Article 55 UUPS provides a legal framework for resolving disputes formally and fairly, involving mediators, arbitrators or courts if necessary.

Tenth, Goal Programming as a health level Decision Support System. Goal Programming is a mathematical optimization method used to solve problems with several conflicting goals. In the context of Bank Bukopin, Goal Programming is used as a Decision Support System to monitor and improve the health or performance of the bank. By taking into account a number of different goals, such as profitability, liquidity and efficiency, Goal Programming helps banks make appropriate and efficient decisions to achieve various goals.

Eleventh, fuzzy logic for predicting creditworthiness. Fuzzy Logic is an information processing technique that allows handling uncertainty or ambiguity in data or information. In the context of Bank Bukopin, fuzzy logic is used to analyze the feasibility of providing credit to prospective customers. By considering a number of variables that may not have definite values, such as income, credit history, and other factors, fuzzy logic can provide predictions of the probability of creditworthiness.

Twelfth, company acquisition by KB Kookmin based on private placement. Company acquisition is a process in which an entity acquires a majority of the shares or ownership of another company. KB Kookmin most likely refers to Kookmin Bank, which is one of the large banks in South Korea. If KB Kookmin acquires a company based on a private placement at Bank Bukopin, that means KB Kookmin acquired shares in Bank Bukopin directly from a company or private investor, not through a public offering.

Thirteenth, credit card restructuring. Credit card restructuring is a process in which Bank Bukopin makes changes to the terms or payment schedule of its customers' credit cards. The aim is to help customers who are experiencing financial difficulties so that they can pay credit card debt more regularly or in more affordable amounts. This restructuring may involve extending payment terms, reducing interest rates, or eliminating late fees.

Fourteenth, the practice of transferring debt/cessie. The practice of debt transfer, also known as cessie, is when Bank Bukopin transfers or sells certain receivables or credits to another party, such as a debt collection company. By doing this, banks can reduce their credit risk and obtain liquidity more quickly. The party purchasing the debt from the bank will be responsible for collecting payments from the original borrower.

Fifteenth, the use of the Altman method (Z-Score) in predicting the occurrence of financial distress. The Altman method or Z-Score is a prediction model developed by Edward Altman to assess the risk of bankruptcy or financial distress in a company. In the context of Bank Bukopin, the Z-Score is used as a tool to measure the level of financial risk and predict the possibility of the bank experiencing financial difficulties in the future. This method uses certain financial ratios to produce a score or number, which is then used to assess the company's financial stability and health. The lower the Z-Score, the higher the risk of financial distress.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 4 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding Bank Bukopin Syariah and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer loyalty behavior; and (4) Other issues.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan

- Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>

- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi*

bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>